

DATA AND RESOURCE SHARING PLAN

While a formal resource sharing plan is required due to the requested level of support (>\$500K), resource sharing has **voluntarily been at the heart of our highly collaborative phenomics work since its inception.**

The Monarch platform is comprised of multiple open-source, open-access components: **data, ontologies and other standards, and software tools, and algorithms.** We want researchers to be able to easily discover, search, explore, and download our work. We will continue to provide appropriate locations for the research community to access the resources we generate, along with documentation, links to the software, and other information that will help improve the accessibility and reusability of our products. Additionally, we provide communication channels for the community, such as a help desk, mailing lists, video tutorials, social media feeds, public presentations, and workshops, to facilitate two-way communication between project members and outside researchers, as well as enabling users to engage with each other. Use of GitHub issue trackers enables community members to submit questions, bug reports and suggestions that will be visible not only to project members but to other users as well, consistent with our commitment to transparency and community development.

Our resource sharing plan adheres to the NIH Grant Policy on Sharing of Unique Research Resources including the Sharing of Biomedical Research Resources Principles and Guidelines for Recipients of NIH Grants and Contracts issued in December 1999 (grants.nih.gov/grants/policy/data_sharing/). We are committed to enhancing the value of research and furthering the advancement of public knowledge. All resources developed by the project will be made available to the scientific community under the terms specified by NIH policy. Both software and resources will be released with licenses that enable further reuse, modification, and redistribution by downstream users and developers. Throughout the development process, key releases of software or data will be deposited in Zenodo, generating an associated DOI. We will evaluate our data sharing according to the rigorous rubrics we worked to develop[3–5].

Software

We always make a **standard and stable version of each piece of code available** for public download. The data and source code generated by this project will continue to be **stored in GitHub**. GitHub records basic metadata such as dates when changes were made, and by whom, and commit messages from developers. We also include documentation for users and software developers, in easy to view sites such as Read The Docs (readthedocs.org), to facilitate reuse of the software. In GitHub progress is trackable as code is committed and pushed and stable releases are created. Where practicable and useful, we will also continue to make our software accessible via REST APIs (see also data access methods below).

Our software licensing strategy:

In establishing a policy for software releases, we are guided by the philosophy that the software we produce should find the widest audience for dissemination and that should there be no hurdles for any legitimate investigator to access the software tools. All software written for this project will be released under the most liberal license possible given institutional limitations, with the default being the BSD 3-Clause License (opensource.org/licenses/BSD-3-Clause).

1. Allows all intellectual properties (IP) generated from the proposed research, including code developed to implement algorithms, data transformation scripts, and other functionalities of the system to be **freely available to everyone at no cost**. This includes researchers and educators in academic institutions, non-profit organizations and government laboratories, as well as for-profit companies;
2. **Allows all community members to modify** the software and share their changes under the same licensing model;

3. Makes it possible for anyone (not just members of our collaboration) to **freely commercialize advanced or customized versions** of the software or incorporate modified versions of portions of our code into commercial software packages, thereby increasing dissemination; and
4. Requires **licensing information to be included** with all distributed software products, including those modified by others.

We will encourage those who fork, modify or add to our code to submit it to GitHub to be considered for inclusion into our overall codebase.

Major components of the existing Monarch software stack and where to find them

Component	Description	Website or Documentation	Repository address
Dipper	data ingest pipeline	dipper.readthedocs.io	github.com/monarch-initiative/dipper
Monarch portal	User interface	monarchinitiative.org	github.com/monarch-initiative/monarch-app
k-BOOM	Algorithm to auto-generate mappings between the elements of different disease terminology sources.	2019 BiorXiv [6]	github.com/monarch-initiative/kboom
OwlSim	Ontology-based profile matching	berkeleybop.org/software/owlsim	github.com/monarch-initiative/owlsim-v3
Phenol	Phenotype Ontology Library	phenol.readthedocs.io	github.com/monarch-initiative/phenol
HPO Case Annotator	Next-generation biocuration app for annotating cases and PhenoPackets.	N/A	github.com/monarch-initiative/HpoCaseAnnotator
PhenoteFX	A Java app that is designed to help create and maintain Human Phenotype Ontology annotation files.	phenotefx.readthedocs.io	github.com/monarch-initiative/PhenoteFX
Exomiser	A tool to annotate and prioritize exome variants	exomiser.github.io/Exomiser/general	github.com/exomiser/Exomiser
Web HIPPO	Deriving insight from the medical literature by fuzzy semantic searches over diseases and phenotypes.	hippo.monarchinitiative.org	github.com/monarch-initiative/web-hippo
Phenogrid	Phenogrid is a Javascript component that visualizes semantic similarity calculations provided by OWLSim, as provided through APIs from the Monarch Initiative.	(Component in monarchinitiative.org portal)	github.com/monarch-initiative/phenogrid

Timeline: All of the resources and products that are generated, whether software, data, or standards, will be released early and often, and at least quarterly under a standard open license where permitted by the original sources. Versions of each will have stable persistent URLs so that they can be readily identified for reference in publications.

Data

The underlying data in Monarch are derived from multiple external sources[1,2] (<https://monarchinitiative.org/about/sources>) the use and secondary use of which is governed by the corresponding original license for each source. As we have described in detail, this is not without complex licensing implications for data integrators and their users [3]. Although it is not possible for Monarch (or for any aggregator) to legally provide unified data sources under a unified license, we will continue to make our data available via multiple mechanisms and we will abide by any and all sharing restrictions placed by the original provider including but not limited to appropriate citation of all the data sources that we use.

Access method	Description	Available formats	URL
API	Programmatic access to associations of individual entities	JSON	api.monarchinitiative.org/api
Downloads	Downloads of single datasets or the whole Monarch graph, including the proposed uPheno-compliant cross-organism mapping files.	RDF (whole datasets), TAB (subsets) as well as our Neo4j database, Solr index are also publicly available in this archive.	data.monarchinitiative.org and archive.monarchinitiative.org/latest
Interface	Ontology-aware, browsable, searchable knowledge graph	Download any result in TAB format	Via monarchinitiative.org
Evaluation data for algorithms	Downloads of publicly available solved clinical cases [proposed herein]	Download as phenopackets	[proposed herein]

This plan reflects that data sharing is an essential aspect of responsible scientific conduct and, in particular, that data gathered with NIH funding should be made publicly available in a time period that assures appropriate confidentiality until the data are accepted for publication, but that also gives the research community and the public at large prompt access to potentially important findings. **That time period is defined as a maximum of 1 year from the final generation of data. This estimate is based on our experience with large studies to balance data quality and rigor with maximizing data access and fostering data re-use.**

HIPAA and Human Subjects

The data sets we propose to use here are publicly available and thus do not generate any privacy or confidentiality concerns. However, because Monarch sits in a complex translational landscape we have -- for good measure -- included a separate Human Subjects section.

NIH Data Commons

The work of the proposed project will not directly generate any data suitable for deposit in the NIH Commons; however, the resources that we will create are highly relevant to that project. In time, the Monarch resources will help to prospectively unify the Data Commons content as the platform comes into fruition. To this end, we have successfully piloted the use of Mondo in the context of semantic search for discovery within the NHLBI STAGE Data Commons. Our goal is to make the Monarch data as widely discoverable and reusable as possible while maintaining the provenance and attribution.

Standards for data annotation and exchange

Input and output data will be annotated with ontology terms from an appropriate OBO Foundry ontology, where available. Those annotations will be stored in a CSV file. All data will be made available in non-proprietary formats.

Data and exchange standards

Standard	Description	GitHub Repo	Website or documentation	License
Phenopackets	An open standard for sharing disease and phenotype information will improve our ability to understand, diagnose, and treat both rare and common diseases.	github.com/phenopackets	phenopackets.org	BSD3
uPheno ontology pattern templates	Cross-modality, cross-species design patterns	github.com/obophenotype/upheno	ebi.ac.uk/ols/ontologies/upheno	CC0 1.0 Universal
BioLink-Model	A high-level data model for representing biological and biomedical knowledge.	github.com/biolink/biolink-model	biolink.github.io/biolink-model	CC0
Monarch API	A lightweight API for exchange of information that sits on top of the Monarch knowledge graph	github.com/biolink/biolink-api	github.com/biolink/biolink-api/blob/master/README.md	BSD3

Ontologies

Ontology	Website	GitHub Repo	License
HPO	hpo.jax.org and ebi.ac.uk/ols/ontologies/hp	github.com/obophenotype/human-phenotype-ontology	Custom no derivatives license (The most similar standard license is CC-BY ND)
SEPIO	obofoundry.org/ontology/seprio and ebi.ac.uk/ols/ontologies/seprio	github.com/monarch-initiative/SEPIO-ontology	CC-BY 3.0
Mondo	monarch-initiative.github.io/mondo and ebi.ac.uk/ols/ontologies/mondo	https://github.com/monarch-initiative/mondo	CC-BY 3.0
MAXO	N/A	https://github.com/monarch-initiative/MAXO	CC-BY 3.0
uPheno	obofoundry.org/ontology/upheno and ebi.ac.uk/ols/ontologies/upheno	github.com/obophenotype/upheno	CC0 1.0 Universal
GENO	obofoundry.org/ontology/geno and ebi.ac.uk/ols/ontologies/geno	https://github.com/monarch-initiative/GENO-ontology	CC-BY 3.0

Protocol and Reagent Sharing Plan

The proposed project will generate only digital (software and data) resources, not material resources. No protocols, organisms, or reagents will be used or generated.

SHARING PLAN LITERATURE CITED

1. McMurry JA, Köhler S, Washington NL, Balhoff JP, Borromeo C, Brush M, et al. Navigating the Phenotype Frontier: The Monarch Initiative. *Genetics*. 2016;203: 1491–1495. doi:10.1534/genetics.116.188870
2. Monarch Initiative Explorer. [cited 22 Oct 2019]. Available: <http://beta.monarchinitiative.org/about/data-sources>
3. Carbon S, Champieux R, McMurry JA, Winfree L, Wyatt LR, Haendel MA. An analysis and metric of reusable data licensing practices for biomedical resources. *PLoS One*. 2019;14: e0213090. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0213090
4. Haendel M, Su A, McMurry J. FAIR-TLC: Metrics to Assess Value of Biomedical Digital Repositories: Response to RFI NOT-OD-16-133. 2016. doi:10.5281/zenodo.203295
5. (Re)usable Data Project. [cited 23 Oct 2019]. Available: <http://reusabledata.org>
6. Mungall CJ, Koehler S, Robinson P, Holmes I, Haendel M. k-BOOM: A Bayesian approach to ontology structure inference, with applications in disease ontology construction. *bioRxiv*. 2019. p. 048843. doi:10.1101/048843